

iAtlantic Deliverable 7.3

CATALOGUE OF iATLANTIC RESOURCES

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The GEOSS All-Atlantic Ocean Data Community Portal (AAOD) - A searchable metadata catalogue of iAtlantic resources

As a participant of the H2020's Open Research Data Pilot¹, iAtlantic's Data Management Plan and Data Policy have been designed to provide the consortium partners with a state-of-the-art data handling workflow in accordance with the FAIR principles (ensuring data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable). The iAtlantic consortium is capitalising on existing data from a large variety of sources, in addition to its own cruise and experimental portfolio. However, to establish a more global, long-term sustainable and searchable dissemination platform for Atlantic data resources in the effort to build an All-Atlantic Data Space² and to achieve active community participation, iAtlantic has collaborated with ESA, CNR-IIA (Italy), the AtlantOS Initiative³, the AANCHOR Project and its H2020 Sister Projects to build an All-Atlantic Ocean Data Community Portal (AAOD)⁴ on the GEOSS Portal Platform⁵, the Global Earth Observing System of Systems. The AAOD was launched in December 2021 (iAtlantic D7.2)⁶ aiming to draw together the international Atlantic observation community by strengthening and growing the network of actors in Atlantic Ocean observations, and to integrate data resources from across the Atlantic in a searchable metadata catalogue with direct data access provisions.

Figure 1. GEOSS All-Atlantic Ocean Data Community Portal - Detailed view of the search dialogue showing the direct integration of the AtlantOS data catalogue.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

² https://allatlanticocean.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/AA-DATA2030_8_9_Roadmap_OS_FINAL.pdf

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/633211>

⁴ <https://www.geoportal.org/community/aaod>

⁵ <https://www.geoportal.org/>

⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/818123/results>

Today, at the end of the project period, the AAOD has successfully integrated a long list of Atlantic data resources and developed into a one-stop web portal to find and retrieve a unique breadth of Atlantic research data and observation resources which are openly available. This includes nearly all iAtlantic-related datasets and a large number of datasets related to its All-Atlantic Sister Projects (Table 1), as well as data records from the centralised catalogue of EMODnet, the European Marine Observation and Data Network. A dedicated iAtlantic Community page⁷ on the EMODnet website links to the AAOD providing users with an additional access point. The content of the “Catalogue of iAtlantic Resources” (D7.3) represents a subset of the AAOD, which currently includes a total of 228 iAtlantic data publications. Almost all iAtlantic data resources are findable and fully accessible through the AAOD portal, which represents 96% of all datasets listed under the specific project results section in CORDIS⁵. These datasets are published in the four data repositories: PANGAEA – Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science⁸ (189 records), SEANOE – Sea Scientific Open Data Edition⁹ (27 records), Zenodo¹⁰ (8 records) and SAEON – South African Environmental Observation Network¹¹ (4 records).

Table 1. Comparative assessment of Findability (%) for datasets published by the iAtlantic project and several All-Atlantic Sister Projects via the AAOD portal vs. OpenAIRE search results reported in CORDIS⁵.

Project Acronym	Grant Agreement - Persistent ID	CORDIS Datasets via OpenAIRE (#)	GEOSS Datasets via GEO-DAB (#)	Findability via GEOSS (%)
iAtlantic	doi:10.3030/818123	237	228	96
AtlantOS	doi:10.3030/633211	108	97	90
MEESO	doi:10.3030/817669	7	6	86
SUMMER	doi:10.3030/817806	122	87	71
AtlantECO	doi:10.3030/862923	74	45	61
Atlas	doi:10.3030/678760	158	83	53
TRIATLAS	doi:10.3030/817578	194	55	28
SO-CHIC	doi:10.3030/821001	17	4	24

The WP7 team and GEOSS Portal Plus (GPP) project partners (ESA, CNR-IIA, SERCO) invested significant efforts to further develop the portal user experience, data search functionality and to customise the AAOD by providing community-specific use cases and requirements collected within the wider iAtlantic consortium and AANChOR JPA networks. In particular, the search results dialogue (Figure 2) has been continuously modified to finally meet the specific requirements of the research community. The completion of the customised AAOD with the support of the GPP Project and integration of the co-existing AtlantOS Earth Observation Catalogue represent significant stepping stones towards establishing the envisioned All-Atlantic Data Space.

⁷ <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/iatlantic-community-page>

⁸ <https://pangaea.de>

⁹ <https://www.seanoe.org/>

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/communities/iatlantic-project-collection>

¹¹ <https://catalogue.saeon.ac.za/>

Figure 2. AAOD - Example of the search results for the query “iAtlantic” returning a total of 219 records (search run on 10/05/2024) with an opened filter on details on the particular data publishers.

The GEOSS Portal is a global initiative and ensures a global reach, addressing the widest possible number of users and stakeholders. The GEOSS portal architecture and infrastructure thus enables the integration and networking of South and North Atlantic data resources within the framework of iAtlantic with reference to the Belem and Galway statements. Although only four datasets published in SAEON are thus far related to iAtlantic, it is evident that the complete and fully automated integration (completed in June 2023) of the SAEON catalogue into the GEOSS platform, and thus into the AAOD, represents a key development step, enabling almost complete end-to-end verification of the metadata management and publication processes.

All SAEON datasets are now accessible through the GEOSS portal. In particular, the Marine Information Management System (MIMS)¹² datasets provided through SAEON are being disseminated through the GEOSS portal and AAOD. The successful integration with GEOSS has enabled SAEON to assume the role of primary research data repository for data publications by iAtlantic and its Sister Projects from the South Atlantic region. This is a significant milestone in improving the visibility and accessibility of South Atlantic data resources, which remains a high priority for the All-Atlantic research community.

¹² <https://data.ocean.gov.za/about/>

Appendix I – Catalogue of iAtlantic data resources accessible via the AAOB

Table 2. Full list of iAtlantic data resources findable and accessible via the All-Atlantic Ocean Data Community Portal (AAOD) on the GEOSS Platform. All datasets have been published by iAtlantic project partners and/or with support of H2020 iAtlantic funding. Data publications are sorted by year of publication and in alphabetical order (leading author first name). List of Data Repositories: PANGAEA – Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science, SEANOE – Sea Scientific Open Data Edition, SAEON – South African Environmental Observation Network.

#	Full Data Citation	Data Repository
1	Hutchinson, K., Henry, T., Luyt, H., Bournman, T., Burger, J., Flynn, R., Reuben Audh, R., Smith, S., Spence, K., & Fawcett, S. (2019). CTD data from the Weddell Sea Expedition 2019 (Version 1) [dataset]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3357972	Zenodo
2	Mohn, C., Gary, S., & van Oevelen, D. (2019). Data set for initializing and forcing of high-resolution local area model implementations in two ATLAS case study areas, Rockall Bank and Condor Seamount [dataset]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3582932	Zenodo
3	Chiessi, C. M., Mulitza, S., Taniguchi, N. K., Prange, M., de Carvalho Campos, M., Häggi, C., Schefuß, E., Pinho, T. M. L., Frederichs, T., Portilho-Ramos, R. C., Sousa, S. H., Crivellari, S., & Cruz, F. W. (2020a). Geochemical and physical parameters of sediment core GeoB16204-2 [dataset]. In: Chiessi, CM et al. (2020): Radiocarbon age, geochemical and physical parameters of sediment core GeoB16204-2 [dataset publication series]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.921255 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.921253	PANGAEA
4	Chiessi, C. M., Mulitza, S., Taniguchi, N. K., Prange, M., de Carvalho Campos, M., Häggi, C., Schefuß, E., Pinho, T. M. L., Frederichs, T., Portilho-Ramos, R. C., Sousa, S. H., Crivellari, S., & Cruz, F. W. (2020b). Radiocarbon age, geochemical and physical parameters of sediment core GeoB16204-2 [dataset]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.921255	PANGAEA
5	Chiessi, C. M., Mulitza, S., Taniguchi, N. K., Prange, M., de Carvalho Campos, M., Häggi, C., Schefuß, E., Pinho, T. M. L., Frederichs, T., Portilho-Ramos, R. C., Sousa, S. H., Crivellari, S., & Cruz, F. W. (2020c). Radiocarbon ages of sediment core GeoB16204-2 [dataset]. In: Chiessi, CM et al. (2020): Radiocarbon age, geochemical and physical parameters of sediment core GeoB16204-2 [dataset publication series]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.921255 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.921254	PANGAEA
6	Hauss, H., & Hoving, H.-J. T. (2020a). Hydrochemistry during POSEIDON cruise POS520 [dataset]. In: Stenvers, Vanessa; Hauss, Helena; Freitas, Rui; Neitzel, Philipp; Osborn, Karen; Robison, Bruce H; Hoving, Henk-Jan T (2020): Pyrosoma atlanticum in the eastern tropical North Atlantic (ETNA) [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918915 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.919340	PANGAEA

#	Full Data Citation	Data Repository
7	Haus, H., & Hoving, H.-J. T. (2020b). Hydrochemistry during POSEIDON cruise POS532 [dataset]. In: Stenvers, Vanessa; Haus, Helena; Freitas, Rui; Neitzel, Philipp; Osborn, Karen; Robison, Bruce H; Hoving, Henk-Jan T (2020): Pyrosoma atlanticum in the eastern tropical North Atlantic (ETNA) [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918915 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.919341	PANGAEA
8	Horton, T. (2020). Scavenging Amphipods, Porcupine Abyssal Plain Sustained Observatory, North Atlantic, 1985-2016 [dataset]. Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS). https://doi.org/10.15468/2akju5	OBIS
9	Hoving, H.-J. T., Christiansen, S., Haus, H., Neitzel, P., Kiko, R., Robison, B. H., Silva, P., & Körtzinger, A. (2020a). Annotation data of video collected during Maria S. Merian cruise MSM49 with the pelagic in situ observation system (PELAGIOS) [dataset]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.919335	PANGAEA
10	Hoving, H.-J. T., Christiansen, S., Haus, H., Neitzel, P., Kiko, R., Robison, B. H., Silva, P., & Körtzinger, A. (2020b). Distribution and abundance of pelagic organisms observed by PELAGIOS during Maria S. Merian cruise MSM49 [dataset]. In: Hoving, H-JT et al. (2020): Annotation data of video collected during Maria S. Merian cruise MSM49 with the pelagic in situ observation system (PELAGIOS) [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.919335 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.919333	PANGAEA
11	Hoving, H.-J. T., Christiansen, S., Haus, H., Neitzel, P., Kiko, R., Robison, B. H., Silva, P., & Körtzinger, A. (2020c). Images of pelagic organisms observed by PELAGIOS during Maria S. Merian cruise MSM49 [dataset]. In: Hoving, H-JT et al. (2020): Annotation data of video collected during Maria S. Merian cruise MSM49 with the pelagic in situ observation system (PELAGIOS) [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.919335 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.919334	PANGAEA
12	Kaufmann, M., Springer, B., Krahmann, G., & Christiansen, B. (2020). Physical oceanography during Maria S. Merian cruise MSM49 [dataset]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910346	PANGAEA
13	Kazanidis, G., Henry, L.-A., Vad, J., Johnson, C., De Clippele, L. H., & Roberts, J. M. (2020a). ATLAS Mingulay Reef Complex Macrobenthos and Environmental Data [dataset]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.915974	PANGAEA
14	Kazanidis, G., Henry, L.-A., Vad, J., Johnson, C., De Clippele, L. H., & Roberts, J. M. (2020b). Environmental settings at stations from Mingulay Reef Complex (MRC) [dataset]. In: Kazanidis, G et al. (2020): ATLAS Mingulay Reef Complex Macrobenthos and Environmental Data [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.915974 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911552	PANGAEA
15	Kazanidis, G., Henry, L.-A., Vad, J., Johnson, C., De Clippele, L. H., & Roberts, J. M. (2020c). Presence/absence matrix of macrobenthos from the Mingulay Reef Complex (MRC) across 79 stations over the years 2003, 2005, 2009, 2010 and 2011 [dataset]. In: Kazanidis, G et al. (2020): ATLAS Mingulay Reef Complex Macrobenthos and Environmental Data [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.915974 .	PANGAEA

#	Full Data Citation	Data Repository
	PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911551	
16	Krahmann, G., Hauss, H., Schütte, F., & Hoving, H.-J. T. (2020a). Physical oceanography during POSEIDON cruise POS520 [dataset]. In: Stenvers, Vanessa; Hauss, Helena; Freitas, Rui; Neitzel, Philipp; Osborn, Karen; Robison, Bruce H; Hoving, Henk-Jan T (2020): Pyrosoma atlanticum in the eastern tropical North Atlantic (ETNA) [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918915 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.919326	PANGAEA
17	Krahmann, G., Hauss, H., Schütte, F., & Hoving, H.-J. T. (2020b). Physical oceanography during POSEIDON cruise POS532 [dataset]. In: Stenvers, Vanessa; Hauss, Helena; Freitas, Rui; Neitzel, Philipp; Osborn, Karen; Robison, Bruce H; Hoving, Henk-Jan T (2020): Pyrosoma atlanticum in the eastern tropical North Atlantic (ETNA) [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918915 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.919327	PANGAEA
18	Langley, B., Halloran, P., Power, A., Rickaby, R., Prabhjoat Chana, Diver, P., Thornalley, D., Hacker, C., & Love, J. (2020). ImageStream Data of Isolating Coccospheres within Sediment [dataset]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3979045	Zenodo
19	Lim, A. (2020). UCC Bathymetric and Backscatter grids of the Porcupine Abyssal Plain [dataset]. In University College Cork. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.916052	PANGAEA
20	Lim, A., & Wheeler, A. J. (2020). UCC Bathymetric grid of the Porcupine Bank Canyon [dataset]. In University College Cork. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.916075	PANGAEA
21	Rakka, M., Maier, S. R., van Oevelen, D., Bilan, M., Godinho, A., Orejas, C., & Carreiro-Silva, M. (2020). Feeding biology of two common habitat-forming octocorals in the Azores Archipelago [dataset]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.913184	PANGAEA
22	Stenvers, V. (2020a). Pyrosoma atlanticum abundance from multinet stations during POSEIDON cruises POS520 and POS532 [dataset]. In: Stenvers, Vanessa; Hauss, Helena; Freitas, Rui; Neitzel, Philipp; Osborn, Karen; Robison, Bruce H; Hoving, Henk-Jan T (2020): Pyrosoma atlanticum in the eastern tropical North Atlantic (ETNA) [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918915 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918870	PANGAEA
23	Stenvers, V. (2020b). Pyrosoma atlanticum organism annotations of JAGO video transects during POSEIDON cruise POS532 [dataset]. In: Stenvers, Vanessa; Hauss, Helena; Freitas, Rui; Neitzel, Philipp; Osborn, Karen; Robison, Bruce H; Hoving, Henk-Jan T (2020): Pyrosoma atlanticum in the eastern tropical North Atlantic (ETNA) [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918915 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918914	PANGAEA

#	Full Data Citation	Data Repository
24	Stenvers, V. (2020c). <i>Pyrosoma atlanticum</i> organism annotations of OFOS video transects during POSEIDON cruise POS532 [dataset]. In: Stenvers, Vanessa; Hauss, Helena; Freitas, Rui; Neitzel, Philipp; Osborn, Karen; Robison, Bruce H; Hoving, Henk-Jan T (2020): <i>Pyrosoma atlanticum</i> in the eastern tropical North Atlantic (ETNA) [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918915 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918916	PANGAEA
25	Stenvers, V. (2020d). <i>Pyrosoma atlanticum</i> organism annotations of PELAGIOS video transects during POSEIDON cruises POS520 and POS532 [dataset]. In: Stenvers, Vanessa; Hauss, Helena; Freitas, Rui; Neitzel, Philipp; Osborn, Karen; Robison, Bruce H; Hoving, Henk-Jan T (2020): <i>Pyrosoma atlanticum</i> in the eastern tropical North Atlantic (ETNA) [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918915 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918907	PANGAEA
26	Stenvers, V., Hauss, H., Freitas, R., Neitzel, P., Osborn, K., Robison, B. H., & Hoving, H.-J. T. (2020). <i>Pyrosoma atlanticum</i> in the eastern tropical North Atlantic (ETNA) [dataset]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918915	PANGAEA
27	Van Audenhaege, L., Arnaubec, A., & Matabos, M. (2020). Eiffel Tower hydrothermal edifice of 2020 (Lucky Strike hydrothermal vent field, Mid Atlantic Ridge): 3D scene and imagery [dataset]. SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/92219	SEANOE
28	Dominguez-Carrió, C., Taranto, G. H., Ramos, M., Ocaña, O. V., Fauconnet, L., Gonçalves, E. J., Carreiro-Silva, M., & Morato, T. (2021). Blue Azores Program Expedition 2018, Station 57, Dive 15: Annotation of <i>Paragorgia johnsoni</i> Gray, 1862 [dataset]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4727164	Zenodo
29	Fröhberg, N., & Paul, S. A. L. (2021). Porewater oxygen profiles in surface sediments of the North Atlantic Basin during RV Maria S. Merian cruise MSM96 [dataset]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.931647	PANGAEA
30	Gazis, I.-Z., Mohrmann, J., Schoening, T., & Wölfl, A.-C. (2021). Multibeam bathymetry processed data (Kongsberg EM 122 working area dataset) of RV MARIA S. MERIAN during cruise MSM96 [dataset]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.930063	PANGAEA
31	Matabos, M., Sarradin, P.-M., Legrand, J., Van Audenhaege, L., Moreau, B., & Cannat, M. (2021). Thermistor chain temperature data from the EMSO-Azores observatory, 2020-2021 [dataset]. SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/84226	SEANOE
32	Mohrmann, J., Gazis, I.-Z., Schoening, T., & Wölfl, A.-C. (2021). Multibeam bathymetry raw data (Kongsberg EM 122 entire dataset) of RV MARIA S. MERIAN during cruise MSM96 [dataset]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.929091	PANGAEA
33	Nascimento, R. A., Santos, T., Venancio, I. M., Chiessi, C. M., Ballalai, J. M., Kuhnert, H., Govin, A., Portilho-Ramos, R. C., Lessa, D. V. de O., Dias, B. B., Pinho, T. M. L., Crivellari, S., Mulitza, S., & Albuquerque, A. L. (2021a). Origin of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ minimum events in thermocline and intermediate waters of the	PANGAEA

#	Full Data Citation	Data Repository
	western South Atlantic [dataset]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936785	
34	Nascimento, R. A., Santos, T., Venancio, I. M., Chiessi, C. M., Ballalai, J. M., Kuhnert, H., Govin, A., Portilho-Ramos, R. C., Lessa, D. V. de O., Dias, B. B., Pinho, T. M. L., Crivellari, S., Mulitza, S., & Albuquerque, A. L. (2021b). $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of benthic foraminifera <i>Cibicides</i> spp. From sediment core GL-1180 [dataset]. In: Nascimento, RA et al. (2021): Origin of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ minimum events in thermocline and intermediate waters of the western South Atlantic [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936785 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936784	PANGAEA
35	Nascimento, R. A., Santos, T., Venancio, I. M., Chiessi, C. M., Ballalai, J. M., Kuhnert, H., Govin, A., Portilho-Ramos, R. C., Lessa, D. V. de O., Dias, B. B., Pinho, T. M. L., Crivellari, S., Mulitza, S., & Albuquerque, A. L. (2021c). $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of planktonic foraminifera <i>Globorotalia inflata</i> from sediment core GL-1090 [dataset]. In: Nascimento, RA et al. (2021): Origin of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ minimum events in thermocline and intermediate waters of the western South Atlantic [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936785 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936780	PANGAEA
36	Nascimento, R. A., Santos, T., Venancio, I. M., Chiessi, C. M., Ballalai, J. M., Kuhnert, H., Govin, A., Portilho-Ramos, R. C., Lessa, D. V. de O., Dias, B. B., Pinho, T. M. L., Crivellari, S., Mulitza, S., & Albuquerque, A. L. (2021d). $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of planktonic foraminifera <i>Globorotalia truncatulinoides</i> from sediment core GL-1180 [dataset]. In: Nascimento, RA et al. (2021): Origin of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ minimum events in thermocline and intermediate waters of the western South Atlantic [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936785 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936782	PANGAEA
37	Nascimento, R. A., Santos, T., Venancio, I. M., Chiessi, C. M., Ballalai, J. M., Kuhnert, H., Govin, A., Portilho-Ramos, R. C., Lessa, D. V. de O., Dias, B. B., Pinho, T. M. L., Crivellari, S., Mulitza, S., & Albuquerque, A. L. (2021e). $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of planktonic foraminifera <i>Neogloboquadrina dutertrei</i> from sediment core GL-1248 [dataset]. In: Nascimento, RA et al. (2021): Origin of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ minimum events in thermocline and intermediate waters of the western South Atlantic [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936785 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936783	PANGAEA
38	Portilho-Ramos, R. C., Titschack, J., Wienberg, C., Siccha, M., Yokoyama, Y., & Hebbeln, D. (2021a). Age determination of sediment core GeoB6718-2 [dataset]. In: Portilho-Ramos, RC et al. (2021): Major environmental drivers determining life and death of cold-water corals through time [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932775 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932760	PANGAEA
39	Portilho-Ramos, R. C., Titschack, J., Wienberg, C., Siccha, M., Yokoyama, Y., & Hebbeln, D. (2021b). Age determination of sediment core GeoB14885-1 [dataset]. In: Portilho-Ramos, RC et al. (2021): Major environmental drivers determining life and death of cold-water corals through time [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932775 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932759	PANGAEA
40	Portilho-Ramos, R. C., Titschack, J., Wienberg, C., Siccha, M., Yokoyama, Y., & Hebbeln, D. (2021c). Benthic foraminifera accumulation rate of sediment core GeoB1813-1 [dataset]. In: Portilho-Ramos, RC et al. (2021): Major environmental drivers determining life and death of cold-water corals through time [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932775 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932737	PANGAEA

#	Full Data Citation	Data Repository
41	Portilho-Ramos, R. C., Titschack, J., Wienberg, C., Siccha, M., Yokoyama, Y., & Hebbeln, D. (2021d). Benthic foraminiferal data of sediment core GeoB6718-2, Porcupine Seabight [dataset]. In: Portilho-Ramos, RC et al. (2021): Major environmental drivers determining life and death of cold-water corals through time [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932775 . PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932719	PANGAEA
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223	Martins, I., Mano, B., Godinho, A., Goulart, J., Sire de Vilar, A., & Carreiro-Silva, M. (2024c). Respiration rates of the cold-water coral <i>Viminella flagellum</i> during a land-based experiment testing the cumulative effect of Cu exposure and ocean acidification [dataset]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.966768	PANGAEA
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